

GAIA Astrometric Error Budget: Proposed approach

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GAIA-LL-043 (V.1)

ABSTRACT. This document describes the proposed approach to the *Astrometry and Astrometric Error Budget* task. An error analysis tree is presented, in which most of the identified error sources are represented. The proposed implementation uses simple text files and fortran programs, controlled by a makefile under Unix/Linux environment, in order to provide the desired flexibility, transparency and integrity of the accuracy model.

1 Introduction

One of the scientific working groups foreseen in the GAIA Science Management Plan is the *Astrometry and Astrometric Error Budget* working group. Its objectives are to maintain the astrometric accuracy model for GAIA, accounting for all identified effects impacting on the final mission accuracies; to include all hardware and modelling effects as they become known; and to monitor the accuracy model of industry, and of the FAME and DIVA missions.

The purpose of this document is to analyse the task of this working group in terms of the required components and actions, and to propose an overall approach for the task. It is expected that the GST and working group members will provide feedback on this proposal in order to proceed to the next step.

2 Purpose of the task

The main task will be to maintain an up-to-date astrometric accuracy model for GAIA, from which an accuracy report can be derived at any time, based on the current best knowledge of the error sources. Other tasks foreseen are in some sense subordinate to this, or depend on the availability of such a model as a reference.

‘Maintaining the model’ means that it is kept in a form that makes it simple to introduce new elements (e.g. error sources as they are identified), and to investigate the consequences of modifications to any of the assumptions. Key issues here are completeness (that all relevant error sources are included), flexibility (that it is easy to make changes), transparency (that effects are not hidden in obscure formulae or ‘black box’ programs), and integrity (that all dependencies are taken into account).

As the model develops, it is important to have one or a few simple *reference cases* to consider, e.g. sky averages of a particular type of star at certain magnitudes. However, with the kind of flexibility we have in mind, it should be easy to investigate any number of special cases.

3 Error sources and error propagation

At the ESTEC meeting in June 2001 (Scientific Preparations for GAIA), I presented a tentative list of ‘things to consider’ in the accuracy assessment. This list, with a few additions, is reproduced here as Table 1.

Each effect should be classified as to how it enters the error budget, and then quantified according to the assumptions (this will often require some separate *ad hoc* calculation or simulation).

In reality, error propagation is horrendously complicated, with statistical correlations and non-gaussian distributions entering at every step. The purpose of the accuracy model is to represent this with something that is simple and transparent, yet (hopefully) realistic. The classical approach is to ignore non-gaussianness and correlations, or rather to assume that correlations are either 0 or 1 (over a certain time scale). This leads to a hierarchic model that can be written, in terms of the variances:

$$v = v_0 + f_1 \times (v_1 + f_2 \times (v_2 + f_3 \times (v_3 + \dots + f_n \times v_n))) \quad (1)$$

where v_k is the sum of all variances contributing on the k -th level, and f_k the factor by which these are reduced on the higher level.

The accuracy model for Hipparcos was essentially of this type, with the highest level ($k = 0$) representing the global astrometric errors, the next $k = 1$ containing the abscissa errors, $k = 2$ the frame errors, and $k = 3$ the samples.

For GAIA one could similarly consider the global level ($k = 0$), the field crossing ($k = 1$), the CCD crossing or elementary observation ($k = 2$), and the individual samples ($k = 3$). An important question is whether such a model is sufficient, and indeed if some more sophisticated approach might be feasible.

A complementary way to summarize and visualize the error contributions is in the form of an error tree. An *error budget tree* would specify how the overall target accuracy (e.g. 10 μ s parallax error at $V = 15$) is subdivided into its various allotted contributions, each in principle translating into a specific technical requirement. However, for the present task an *error analysis tree* is more relevant: this is rather like a functional description of how the different error sources enter into the overall accuracy estimate.

Figure 1 shows an error analysis tree, in which (most of) the error sources in Table 1 have been inserted at the appropriate level.

TABLE 1. A list of ‘things to consider’ in the astrometric accuracy assessment.

<p>Source</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – absolute flux – extinction – sky background – statistical microlensing – double/multiple stars – solar-system objects <p>Satellite and environment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – thermal – radiation pressure – solar wind – particle radiation – micrometeorites – real-time attitude determination – attitude control (FEED) <p>Instrument</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – mirror alignment and deformation – polishing errors – optical transmittance – straylight – diffraction spikes – filter characteristics – CCD characteristics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · geometry · quantum efficiency (QE) · modulation transfer function (MTF) · charge transfer efficiency (CTE) · intensity transfer function (ITF) · saturation/bleeding – electronic chain characteristics – discretization and compression – source detection (ASM) – TDI tracking and windowing – distortion and rate errors – chromaticity – evolution (due to radiation damage) of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · transmittance · aberrations (WFE) · charge transfer efficiency (CTE) 	<p>Mission</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – scanning law – mission length – data gaps – source distribution (Galaxy model) – source confusion – data saturation – timing – satellite orbit – orbit determination – barycentric ephemerides – error margins <p>Data analysis</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – reference systems – relativistic effects – detection probabilities – false detections – centroiding algorithm – calibration model – attitude model – astrometric error propagation – outlier treatment – covariance estimation – spin harmonics – large-scale frame distortion – small-scale correlations – parallax zero point – link to extragalactic frame
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FIGURE 1. Error analysis tree for the astrometric accuracy of GAIA.

4 Implementation of the accuracy model

4.1 General ideas

For the practical set-up of the model, the necessary components seem to be:

1. a list of all relevant parameters (name, value) and other assumptions;
2. a list of error sources (with logical switches), and information about how they are taken into account;
3. a numerical or semi-analytical model for the error propagation, including documentation;
4. definition of standard cases to be considered for reference purposes, as well as special cases as required;
5. auxiliary software for certain computations (e.g. scanning law simulation);
6. a tool to synthesise all the other components: essentially this would ensure consistency (e.g. that all elements are updated) and its output could be a ‘raw’ accuracy report for the relevant case or cases.

In addition, full visibility is required, at least for the working group members, and for that purpose it is desirable that the whole thing can be ‘worked’ by anybody who wants to take the trouble to do so. This means that software and data files should be portable and possible to run in standard environments.

Proposed solution:

- Since much of the software is already available in Fortran, that would be the preferred language at least for the major program units.
- For portability and easy inspection, all data files are simple and self-documented text files.
- Program execution is normally controlled by a makefile: this ensures that data files are automatically updated and should run without modification on almost any Unix or Linux platform.
- All files are placed in a password-protected folder under Livelink. This would give easy (read-only) access to data and programs e.g. by all members of the working group. If possible, task leaders should have permission to upload the files.

4.2 A first sketch to fix some ideas

The data files would be of three main types: parameter files, tables, and output files. They could be distinguished by their filename extensions (`*.par`, `*.tab`, `*.out`). For instance,

`ccd.par` would define CCD parameters such as pixel size and numbers, number of phases, diffusion length, etc, while `ccd.tab` could tabulate QE versus wavelength. Parameters and tables need to be systematically divided into many files, otherwise there would be little advantage with the automatic updating through the makefile. For the same reason many of the computations are split into separate programs with intermediate results communicated via output files. The latter could contain text (comments) as well as parameters and tables.

Among the programs currently foreseen are:

`ns1.f` – calculates the Nominal Scanning Law

`scan.f` – calculates the scans across a given point of the sky

`skystat.f` – calculates statistics such as sky averages

`opsf.f` – calculates the optical point spread function

`spsf.f` – calculates the sampled point spread function

`phot.f` – calculates the photometric response

`cent.f` – calculates the centroiding accuracy

`dyna.f` – calculates the dynamical effects on the satellite

`total.f` – calculates the total astrometric errors

Note that most of these can to a large extent be based on existing software described e.g. in SAG-LL-025, 026, 032, 035.

4.3 Use of GDAAS

The GAIA Data Access and Analysis Study (and its future development) provides a partially independent assessment of some of the error sources, in particular related to the Global Iteration Solution concept and calibration accuracies. Indeed, some of these errors can perhaps only be assessed by this kind of large-scale experiments. On the other hand, the accuracy model sketched here is much more flexible in the sense that it is easily used to explore a large number of cases. Thus, the large-scale simulations can be used to calibrate the accuracy model with respect to such error sources.

5 How to proceed from here

Initially, the GST and working group would be asked to comment on the proposed general approach and to suggest possible improvements.

The next step would be to set up the model in sufficient detail to reproduce the accuracy assessment in the Study Report. This would mainly be done by LL, although some input

could be requested from other members. It is important to take the ‘old’ GAIA as the starting point for this exercise, in order to understand any differences that might result with respect to the assessment in the Study Report.

The parameters and assumptions are then modified to represent the revised GAIA design. Compared with the previous exercise, this provides a strictly comparable assessment of the revised mission.

The resulting model would then be made available on Livelink and subsequently updated and improved as the studies progress. At this point the definition of reference cases should also be agreed.

All members should be encouraged to scrutinize the model and all its assumptions. Suggested changes and additions are collected in a separate document until they are implemented.